

The Norwegian Federated European Genome Phenome Archive (FEGA)

The Critical Role of Sharing Human Genetic Data for Research

The exchange of human genetic information is vital for the progression of medical sciences including precision medicine, offering insights into diseases and spearheading the development of novel treatments, therapies, and related strategies for better prevention. Aggregating such data enhances statistical accuracy and accelerates health research. The sharing of such personal/sensitive data must comply with the rigorous privacy protections mandated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ensuring the security of personal data.

Launched in 2022, the Norwegian Federated European Genome Phenome Archive (FEGA) is designed to facilitate the secure and lawful sharing of sensitive human omics data. It capitalizes on technology initially developed by the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) and benefits from strong collaboration with ELIXIR, the European life science data infrastructure. FEGA reflects community-driven standards for sensitive data management, incorporating protocols established by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH).

FEGA employs a federated data access architecture—sensitive data is securely stored within respective local or national jurisdictions, while a centralized portal facilitates the discovery of specific datasets world wide. This arrangement addresses the primary challenges of managing large volumes of human omics data and the associated privacy concerns, by limiting the exposure of sensitive data and allowing for controlled, secure access on a need-to-know basis while providing general metadata about the scope of the datasets.

FEGA is managed by ELIXIR Norway. The access to each study is controlled by its Data Access Committee (DAC). The DAC is responsible for managing data access requests and ensuring that the release of data is in accordance with the GDPR.

By February 2024, the FEGA network expanded to include seven European national nodes, with numerous other national partners actively working to set up their nodes. This expansion is part of a larger vision to foster a global resource enabling robust discovery and access to sensitive human omics data. This network will significantly boost the capacity for conducting large-scale, multi-national disease research, thereby improving patient outcomes.

What are the prerequisites for archiving data in FEGA?

The mechanism of controlled access in FEGA ensures compliance with ethical standards and legal requirements. Researchers and institutions partaking in this framework must adhere to rigorous protocols, including:

1. Data Processing Agreements;

These legal documents between the archiving institution (data controller) and the archive must be in place to detail the nature, scope, and purpose of data processing in line with GDPR demands. In order to access the data, requesting institutions have to sign a Data Access Agreement.

2. Consistent and Clear Consent:

Research participants are required to provide informed consent; the form should clearly articulate how their data will be used, stored, and removed/archived within the FEGA framework.

3. **Ethical approval by REC:** Research that is subject to approval by the regional research ethics committees (RECs) should state the archiving process of data, to FEGA, in their application.

4. **Data Access Committees:** These committees play a critical role in evaluating access requests, ensuring that each request is justified and meets the stringent criteria of data protection and ethical research in an efficient way. They can be formed on a per dataset or institutional basis.

What can be done to facilitate archiving to FEGA?

To optimize FEGA's functionality and its adoption across the research community, the following strategies are suggested:

1. **Increased Education and Awareness:** Enhancing the understanding of FEGA's capabilities and benefits within Norway's research community is critical to foster productive and improved user engagement.

2. **Standardization of Consent Forms:** Streamlining consent forms across studies can facilitate smoother integrations with FEGA's controlled access system and the representation of the participant's consent in machine actionable form.

3. **Robust Data Access Committees:** Establishing routines for mandating and operating committees at the institutions ensures swift and appropriate responses to data access requests and should integrate the expertise of the data generating researchers where possible.

4. **Integration into REC and Consent Procedures:** Researchers should be encouraged to include provisions for FEGA data archiving right from the initiation of their projects, ensuring seamless ethical and legal compliance.

5. **Including FEGA into recommendations and policies:** Including the archiving of relevant data to FEGA into funder and institutional recommendations and policies will incentivize researchers to enable data re-use.

6. **Framework Data Processing agreement:** Setting up data processing agreement frameworks between the institution and FEGA that can be amended for single projects is decreasing the bureaucratic burden for the individual researchers

Conclusion

Enhancing and properly implementing FEGA is essential for advancing Norway's genetic research within ethical and legal frameworks. By solidifying data protection practices, standardizing consent procedures, increasing system awareness, and streamlining access processes, FEGA can vastly improve the landscape of global health research.

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